

FORMATION OF COMPLEX COMPOUNDS BETWEEN LEAD
NITRATE AND ALKALI NITRATES. PART X.
THERMOMETRIC TITRATIONS

BY M. R. NAYAR AND C. S. PANDE

Thermometric titration curves definitely indicate the formation of three complex compounds in the systems : $\text{KNO}_3\text{-Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2\text{-H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{NH}_4\text{NO}_3\text{-Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2\text{-H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{RbNO}_3\text{-Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2\text{-H}_2\text{O}$, whereas in $\text{LiNO}_3\text{-Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2\text{-H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{NaNO}_3\text{-Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2\text{-H}_2\text{O}$ systems there is no indication of complex formation. The observations are in conformity with the results obtained from other physico-chemical properties.

In previous parts of this series (*Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1948, 27A, 284, 343; 1949, 30A, 251), it has been shown that in alkali nitrate-lead nitrate-water systems, three definite complexes are produced in solution in those containing potassium, ammonium or rubidium nitrate, while no such compounds seem to be produced in lithium or sodium nitrate systems. The evidence for the existence of such compounds becomes unequivocal when such widely differing properties like viscosity, conductivity and transport number yield exactly similar results. Attempts have been made here to substantiate these conclusions by thermometric titrations (Dutoit, *J. chim. phys.*, 1921, 19, 324). A search demonstrating the existence and composition of these complex compounds, on the basis of energy changes, is the subject matter of the present communication.

EXPERIMENTAL

The thermometric titration arrangement was similar to that described by Dutt (this *Journal*, 1945, 22, 4) and by Haldar (*ibid.*, 1946, 23, 147). The apparatus consists of a silver calorimeter placed inside a wide mouthed Dewar flask. The solution to be titrated is taken inside the calorimeter the mouth of which is closed by means of a cork provided with three bores. Through one bore passes a Beckmann thermometer reading to 1/100th of a degree, through the second a hand stirrer and through the third passes the tip of the burette. The mouth of the Dewar vessel is further protected by means of a three-bore asbestos sheet. The titre* (lead nitrate) is added from the burette to a fixed volume (24 c.c. of titrant *i. e.* alkali nitrate) and the changes in temperature are noted on the Beckmann thermometer after stirring at a constant rate for a definite period. The conditions of the experiments for the various titrations are maintained as constant as possible. The differences in temperature observed are then plotted against the titre in c. c.

FIG. 1
System: (a) $\text{LiNO}_3 \cdot \text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$
(b) $\text{NaNO}_3 \cdot \text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$

FIG. 2
System: $\text{KNO}_3 \cdot \text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$

FIG. 3

System : $\text{NH}_4\text{NO}_3\text{-Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2\text{-H}_2\text{O}$

FIG. 4

System : $\text{RbNO}_3\text{-Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2\text{-H}_2\text{O}$

The alkali nitrates and lead nitrate (B. D. H/A R.) used were recrystallised thrice with distilled water and dried at 120°. Molar solutions of these reagents were prepared by direct weighing, and were stored in thoroughly cleaned, steamed, glass-stoppered pyrex bottles.

TABLE I

System : $\text{LiNO}_3\text{-Pb(NO}_3)_2\text{-H}_2\text{O}$.
M- LiNO_3 soln. (24 c.c.) and *M*- $\text{Pb(NO}_3)_2$ soln. taken.

$\text{Pb(NO}_3)_2$ added.	Therm. reading.	Rise in temp.	Total rise in temp.	Rise in temp./c.c.	$\text{Pb(NO}_3)_2$ added.	Therm. reading.	Rise in temp.	Total rise in temp.	Rise in temp./c.c.
0 c.c.	4.220	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	26 c.c.	4.534	0.015	0.314	0.0075
2	4.255	0.035	0.035	0.0175	28	4.548	0.014	0.328	0.007
4	4.287	0.032	0.067	0.0160	30	4.561	0.013	0.341	0.0066
6	4.317	0.030	0.097	0.0150	32	4.573	0.012	0.353	0.006
8	4.345	0.028	0.125	0.0140	34	4.584	0.011	0.364	0.0055
10	4.372	0.027	0.152	0.0135	36	4.595	0.011	0.375	0.0055
12	4.398	0.026	0.178	0.0130	38	4.605	0.010	0.385	0.005
14	4.422	0.024	0.202	0.0120	40	4.615	0.010	0.395	0.005
16	4.444	0.022	0.224	0.0110	42	4.625	0.010	0.405	0.005
18	4.465	0.021	0.245	0.0105	44	4.635	0.010	0.415	0.005
20	4.485	0.020	0.265	0.0100	46	4.645	0.010	0.425	0.005
22	4.503	0.018	0.283	0.009	48	4.654	0.009	0.434	0.0045
24	4.519	0.016	0.299	0.008	50	4.663	0.009	0.443	0.0045

TABLE II

System : $\text{NaNO}_3\text{-Pb(NO}_3)_2\text{-H}_2\text{O}$.
M- NaNO_3 solution (24 c. c.) and *M*-lead nitrate soln. taken.

$\text{Pb(NO}_3)_2$ added.	Therm. reading.	Rise in temp.	Total rise in temp.	Rise in temp./c.c.	$\text{Pb(NO}_3)_2$ added.	Therm. reading.	Rise in temp.	Total rise in temp.	Rise in temp./c.c.
0 c.c.	0.780	0.000	0.000	0.0000	26 c.c.	1.263	0.025	0.483	0.0125
2	0.850	0.070	0.070	0.035	28	1.287	0.024	0.507	0.012
4	0.900	0.050	0.120	0.025	30	1.309	0.022	0.529	0.011
6	0.945	0.045	0.165	0.0225	32	1.329	0.020	0.549	0.010
8	0.985	0.040	0.205	0.020	34	1.347	0.018	0.567	0.009
10	1.023	0.038	0.243	0.019	36	1.363	0.016	0.583	0.008
12	1.059	0.036	0.279	0.018	38	1.377	0.014	0.597	0.007
14	1.093	0.034	0.313	0.017	40	1.389	0.012	0.609	0.006
16	1.125	0.032	0.345	0.016	42	1.400	0.011	0.620	0.0055
18	1.155	0.030	0.375	0.015	44	1.410	0.010	0.630	0.005
20	1.184	0.029	0.404	0.0145	46	1.418	0.008	0.638	0.004
22	1.212	0.028	0.432	0.014	48	1.426	0.008	0.646	0.004
24	1.238	0.026	0.458	0.013					

TABLE III

System : $\text{KNO}_3\text{-Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2\text{-H}_2\text{O}$.
M- KNO_3 soln. (25 c.c.) and *M*- $\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ soln. taken.

$\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ added.	Therm. reading.	Rise in temp.	Total rise in temp.	Rise in temp./c.c.	$\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ added.	Therm. reading.	Rise in temp.	Total rise in temp.	Rise in temp./c.c.
0 c.c.	0.620	0.000	0.000	0.000	16 c.c.	1.344	0.030	0.724	0.015
1	0.685	0.065	0.065	0.065	18	1.374	0.030	0.754	0.015
2	0.750	0.065	0.130	0.065	20	1.404	0.030	0.784	0.015
3	0.815	0.063	0.193	0.063	22	1.434	0.030	0.814	0.015
4	0.875	0.062	0.255	0.062	24	1.464	0.030	0.844	0.015
5	0.940	0.065	0.320	0.065	25	1.484	0.020	0.864	0.020
6	1.005	0.065	0.385	0.065	26	1.489	0.005	0.869	0.005
6.25	1.025	0.020	0.405	0.080	28	1.500	0.011	0.880	0.005
7	1.057	0.032	0.437	0.042	30	1.507	0.007	0.887	0.004
8	1.097	0.040	0.477	0.040	32	1.514	0.007	0.894	0.004
9	1.137	0.040	0.517	0.040	36	1.530	0.016	0.910	0.004
10	1.177	0.040	0.557	0.040	40	1.545	0.015	0.925	0.0037
11	1.217	0.040	0.597	0.040	44	1.560	0.015	0.940	0.0037
12	1.257	0.040	0.637	0.040	48	1.574	0.014	0.954	0.0035
12.5	1.289	0.032	0.669	0.064	50	1.582	0.008	0.962	0.004
14	1.314	0.025	0.694	0.016					

TABLE IV

System : $\text{NH}_4\text{NO}_3\text{-Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2\text{-H}_2\text{O}$.
M- NH_4NO_3 (24 c.c.) and *M*- $\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ soln. taken.

$\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ added.	Therm. reading.	Rise in temp.	Total rise in temp.	Rise in temp./c.c.	$\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ added.	Therm. reading.	Rise in temp.	Total rise in temp.	Rise in temp./c.c.
0 c.c.	1.825	0.0000	0.000	0.000	20 c.c.	2.688	0.036	0.863	0.018
1	1.897	0.072	0.072	0.072	22	2.728	0.040	0.903	0.020
2	1.970	0.073	0.145	0.073	23	2.750	0.022	0.925	0.022
3	2.044	0.074	0.219	0.074	24	2.780	0.030	0.955	0.030
4	2.119	0.075	0.294	0.075	26	2.796	0.016	0.971	0.008
5	2.196	0.076	0.371	0.077	28	2.811	0.015	0.986	0.0075
6	2.276	0.080	0.451	0.080	30	2.825	0.014	1.000	0.007
7	2.316	0.040	0.491	0.040	32	2.838	0.013	1.013	0.0065
8	2.358	0.042	0.533	0.042	34	2.850	0.012	1.025	0.006
9	2.401	0.043	0.576	0.043	36	2.861	0.011	1.036	0.0055
10	2.445	0.044	0.620	0.044	38	2.871	0.010	1.046	0.005
11	2.490	0.045	0.665	0.045	40	2.880	0.009	1.055	0.0045
12	2.550	0.060	0.725	0.060	42	2.888	0.008	1.063	0.004
14	2.586	0.036	0.761	0.018	44	2.895	0.007	1.070	0.0035
16	2.618	0.032	0.793	0.016	46	2.901	0.006	1.076	0.003
18	2.652	0.034	0.827	0.017	48	2.907	0.006	1.082	0.003

TABLE V

System : $\text{RbNO}_3\text{-Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2\text{-H}_2\text{O}$.
M-RbNO}_3 soln. (24 c.c.) and *M-Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2* soln. taken.

$\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ added.	Therm. reading.	Rise in temp	Total rise in temp.	Rise in temp./c.c.	$\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ added.	Therm. reading.	Rise in temp.	Total rise in temp.	Rise in temp./c.c.
0 c.c.	2.482	0.000	0.000	0.0000	20 c.c.	3.360	0.044	0.878	0.022
1	2.550	0.068	0.068	0.068	22	3.412	0.052	0.930	0.026
2	2.620	0.070	0.138	0.070	24	3.476	0.064	0.994	0.032
3	2.692	0.072	0.210	0.072	26	3.496	0.020	1.014	0.010
4	2.766	0.074	0.284	0.074	28	3.515	0.019	1.033	0.0095
5	2.843	0.077	0.361	0.077	30	3.533	0.018	1.051	0.009
6	2.925	0.082	0.443	0.082	32	3.550	0.017	1.068	0.0085
7	2.963	0.038	0.481	0.038	34	3.565	0.015	1.083	0.0075
8	3.004	0.041	0.522	0.041	36	3.579	0.014	1.097	0.007
9	3.347	0.043	0.565	0.043	38	3.592	0.013	1.110	0.0065
10	3.092	0.045	0.610	0.045	40	3.604	0.012	1.122	0.006
11	3.140	0.048	0.658	0.048	42	3.615	0.011	1.133	0.0055
12	3.200	0.060	0.718	0.060	44	3.625	0.010	1.143	0.005
13	3.220	0.020	0.738	0.020	46	3.634	0.009	1.152	0.0045
14	3.238	0.018	0.756	0.018	48	3.642	0.008	1.160	0.004
16	3.276	0.038	0.794	0.019	50	3.649	0.007	1.167	0.0035
18	3.316	0.040	0.834	0.200					

Tables I-V indicate the details of observations, viz., the rise in temperature for each addition, total rise in temperature and rise in temperature per c.c. ($\Delta T/c. c.$), after each addition in c.c. of lead nitrate to a definite volume of alkali nitrate. These values are represented graphically in Figures 1-4.

DISCUSSION

An examination of the various graphs indicates that smooth curves are obtained with LiNO_3 and NaNO_3 systems indicating that no compounds are produced, while there are three breaks in each of the curves corresponding respectively to systems containing KNO_3 , NH_4NO_3 and RbNO_3 . These breaks occur (Figs. 2, 3 and 4) at concentrations at which the molecular ratios between lead nitrate and alkali nitrate correspond to the formation of three definite complexes of the formulae :

(a) $4\text{RNO}_3.\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, and (b) $2\text{RNO}_3.\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, (c) $\text{RNO}_3.\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ where R stands for K , NH_4 or Rb .

These results are brought out more prominently when the differential variation of rise in temperature per c. c is plotted against the volume of lead nitrate added. The differential variation curve indicates values of different orders of magnitude, which must correspond to different heats of formation of the compounds. By determining the specific heat of each of the solutions, the heat of dilution, and water equivalent of calorimeter, it is possible to calculate the heat of reaction or heat of formation of each of the compounds. (This is under investigation).

Since sending the paper for publication two articles have appeared independently confirming our results on the basis of entirely different properties (B. K. Narasimhamurthy, *Curr. Sci.*, 1950, 19, 240 ; V. S. Venkatasubramanian, *ibid.*, 1951, 20, 13).

CHEMISTRY DEPARTMENT,
LUCKNOW UNIVERSITY,
LUCKNOW.

Received July 29, 1950.